

**Car traffic changes and wildlife mortality
resulting from the upgrade of the Narewowska road,
Białowieża Forest Natura 2000 site**

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1. Introduction

On 4 March 2016 authorities of Białowieża and Browsk communes issued two decisions allowing jointly to upgrade the Narewowska road, 15.6 km of what for decades was a dirt road running along N-S axis across the northern part of Białowieża Forest Natura 2000 site PLC200004. The upgrade was requested by State Forests Districts Białowieża and Browsk. The decisions were based on the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) report for the upgrade project, prepared by the Bureau of Forest Management and Geodesy, Branch in Białystok (*BULiGL oddział w Białymstoku*) in Autumn of 2015.

The EIA report for the Narewowska road upgrade project concluded that the upgrade will not negatively impact the integrity of the Natura 2000 site. This conclusion was based on several questionable premises. These included:

- Traffic volume forecasted after the upgrade will stay low, at the average level of 46 vehicles per day;
- The speed of vehicles using the upgraded road will remain low, in line with the 30 km/h speed limit imposed for this road section;
- Collisions of wildlife with cars will be unimportant.

Below, we describe more in detail some of the claims of the EIA report for the project.

The traffic volume on the unimproved road was estimated at 30 cars per day in the EIA report, but the source of this data was not provided. Also, the variation around this number was not provided. The authors of the report assumed that after the upgrade, the daily traffic volume will increase by 50% (to 46 cars per day), but no data for this claim were presented. In particular, this value was not linked to any measures of car traffic volumes in the existing road network around the Białowieża Forest.

The hidden assumption presented in the report was that car drives will comply with the speed limit of 30 km/h imposed for the upgraded road. As repeatedly shown in many studies, the numbers of animals killed on the road are linked to the actual speed of vehicles, thus the assumption has important consequences for the assessment of the possible impact of the project on wildlife.

Strikingly, the EIA report was effectively devoid of an analysis of possible impacts of the existing road on the wildlife and adjacent habitats. Despite the plethora of published studies on the effects of roads and vehicle traffic on wildlife and habitats, the authors simply listed several possible impacts to dismiss their importance in single statements, without any serious analyses. Although the possible impact of amphibian and reptile mortality was stated as potentially important, that did not affect the conclusion of no significant impact for the species and habitats protected within the Natura 2000 site.

2. Set-up of the study

To verify the lack of impacts predicted in the EIA report of 2015, we have set up a monitoring scheme aimed to quantitatively assess the actual values of key drivers of anthropogenic pressure resulting from the upgrade of the Narewowska road, i.e. traffic intensity, vehicle speed, and wildlife mortality. From February 2019 to October 2020, we surveyed Narewowska road, covering thus periods both “before” and “after” the official opening of the upgraded road on 03 February 2020. More precisely:

- we have measured actual traffic volume in the period before and after opening the upgraded section of the Narewowska road using camera traps;
- we also have estimated the wildlife mortality on the upgraded road using field surveys of road-kills;
- We have measured the actual speeds of vehicles using Narewowska road after the completed upgrade.

The detailed survey methods are described in the section “Methods”.

3. Results

3.1. Traffic

We measured traffic volume for 489 days between 18 February 2019 and 06 October 2020. This period includes 211 survey days before the official opening of the upgraded road on 03 February 2020 and 278 survey days after the opening of the upgraded road. In total, we surveyed 46,257 vehicles over 489 camera days.

The majority of the recorded road users were various cars (69% before, and 79% after the upgrade), followed by bicycles (27% and 19%, respectively), and motorbikes (1% in both periods). Pedestrians constituted 2 and 1% of road users. Animals were recorded rarely, averaging 0.18 events per day in both periods.

The basic data on road traffic recorded on Narewowska road before and after the upgrade are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Road traffic recorded on Narewowska road using camera traps operating for 489 days between 18 Feb 2019 and 06 Oct 2020. Data are shown separately for the periods before and after opening the upgraded road (211 and 278 days, respectively) on 03 Feb 2020. Totals for vehicles include bicycles, cars, motorbikes, and tractors.

Category / sub-category	Numbers		Percentages	
	Before	After	Before	After
Animals	37	50		
Bicycles	3642	6379	27	19
Cars (total)	9140	26343	69	79
<i>Buses & mini-buses</i>	17	52	0.13	0.16
<i>Passenger cars</i>	8295	25360	63	76
<i>Trucks & lorries</i>	369	337	3	1
<i>Vans</i>	459	594	3	2
Carriages	2	0	0	0
Motorbikes	119	359	1	1
Pedestrians	217	216	2	1
Tractors	124	149	1	0
Total (without animals)	13244	33446		
Total vehicles	13027	33230		

Daily traffic volume (measured here as numbers of cars per day) was dependent on three major factors – status of the road (before/after upgrade), month and day of the week. To estimate the effects of these factors on traffic volume we modelled the average daily traffic volume of cars as a function of road status, month, and day of the week while allowing for interaction between status and month, as well as status and day of the week:

$$\text{Daily traffic volume} \sim \text{status} + \text{month} + \text{day} + \text{status:weekday} + \text{status:month}$$

The largest source of variation in traffic volume was road status. i.e. whether the road was fully upgraded or not. Traffic volume has increased threefold, on average, after the upgraded road was opened, from 29 cars per day to 91 cars per day (Fig. R1). This increase was, however, dependent on the month of the study, with the largest increases observed for July (4 times) and the smallest for April (2 times). After the upgrade, the median number of cars recorded per day was 96, with the maximum reaching 351 cars per day, while prior to the upgrade the median was 24 and the maximum 116.

Fig. R1. Numbers of cars recorded per day on Narewkowska road, shown for the period before and after the upgrade. Thick horizontal lines show medians, boxes represent upper and lower quartiles (25% and 75% of the observations in the sample)

After the upgrade, in 75% of days, the traffic volume exceeded the threshold value of 46 cars per day, compared to 23% before the upgrade. On the upgraded road, in July, August and October, the threshold value was exceeded each day, while in June and September in 93% of days.

Both before and after the upgrade, car traffic showed clear seasonal dynamics, with the lowest daily numbers of cars recorded in late Autumn, Winter, and early Spring, and the highest from July to September (Fig. R2, left panel). Additionally, daily numbers of cars were higher on weekends (starting already on Friday) than on other days of the week (Fig. R2, right panel). After the completed upgrade, maximum numbers of cars were recorded on weekends in July, when the average daily count exceeded 250 cars.

Fig. R2. Numbers of cars recorded per day before and after upgrade of the road, shown in relation to month (left panel) and day of the week (right panel; 1=Monday). Data for the period before upgrade shown in green, for the period after upgrade in red. Presented are effect sizes from the model allowing for interactions between status and month and status and day of the week. Estimates of monthly traffic are shown for Saturday, while estimates for successive days of the week are shown for July. A thin horizontal line marks the value of 46 cars per day forecasted in the EIA as the traffic volume after the upgrade. Dots represent means, and whiskers represent 95% confidence intervals

Within a single day, traffic intensity (cars per hour) was highest around noon and early afternoon (11:00-18:00), with no significant differences in hourly dynamics noted after the completed road upgrade (Fig. R3).

3.2. Wildlife killed on the road

We recorded 509 killed vertebrates in 191 surveys of roadkills conducted on the part of Narewkowska road within 17 months. Allowing for carcass removal and incomplete coverage of the whole road, we estimated that the actual number of killed vertebrates for the whole 15.6 km section of the road was 952 in 17 months. Based on these values we estimated that the annual mortality of vertebrates on the Narewkowska road was about 43 animals per kilometer of the road (672 vertebrate animals for the whole 15.6 km section).

Fig. R3. Variation in the number of cars recorded per hour on Narewkowska road before (upper panel) and after (lower) panel the upgrade. Note different scales on the vertical axes of the panels.

Of the 505 killed vertebrates identified, 51% were amphibians, 28% reptiles, 12% mammals, and 8% birds. Among amphibians, Common Toad (*Bufo bufo*) and brown frogs (*Rana arvalis* and *Rana temporaria*) dominated (120 and 111 roadkills, respectively). Grass Snake (*Natrix natrix*) was the most frequent victim among reptiles (123 individuals). Chaffinch (*Fringilla coelebs*), Robin (*Erithacus rubecula*), and Blackbird (*Turdus merula*) dominated among killed birds. The majority of killed mammals were Shrews (*Sorex* spp.) and Moles (*Talpa europaea*).

Modelling of the vertebrate roadkill numbers revealed that the daily number of victims was positively related to the daily car traffic on the road. The numbers of killed vertebrates significantly increased with the number of cars using the road on a given day.

Apart of the vertebrate kills, we have recorded large numbers (over 3000) of killed invertebrates, mostly insects (chiefly Coleoptera). This suggests that for this group of animals, road-related mortality is several times higher than for vertebrates.

3.3. Speed of cars

We measured the speed of vehicles using the upgraded Narewkowska road on a sample of 87 cars driving the road on 05 and 06 June 2021. The average speed was 52.4 km/h, with 25% of cars exceeding 60 km/h and 5% of cars exceeding 70 km/h (Fig. R4). Maximum recorded speed was 84 km/h. Only 3.5% of cars showed average speed of 30 km/h or less, in line with the speed limit imposed on the road section and used for calculations presented in the EIA. The speed was not related to the type of car nor to the hour of measurement. The average time to cover this stretch of

the Narewowska road was 12.8 minutes, which stays in a close agreement with information presented in Google Maps service showing 12 minutes needed to cover this exact section of the road. The latter information confirms that the vast majority of car drivers using GPS devices regularly drive the Narewowska road with the average speed around 52 km/h.

Fig. R4. The distribution of measured speed of cars using the upgraded Narewowska road in June 2021.

4. Conclusions

- (1) After the completed upgrade the daily traffic volume increased three-fold, from 29 to 91 cars per day. This is in stark contrast to the values forecasted in the EIA for the upgrade project, where the predicted increase was from 30 to 46 cars per day.
- (2) Besides a significant increase in traffic volume following the road upgrade, car traffic showed a clear seasonal and weekly pattern, with more cars using the road in the summer months and on weekends. After the upgrade, the largest numbers of cars were recorded on weekends in July and August, when expected values exceeded 250 cars per day and the recorded maximum was 351 cars per day.
- (3) The road was a significant source of mortality of vertebrates, mainly amphibians and reptiles, but also small mammals and birds. On average, 43 vertebrates were killed annually per single kilometer of the road (672 vertebrates annually for the whole road section). Daily, the number of victims of road collisions increased with the car traffic.
- (4) Only 3.5% of cars using the upgraded Narewowska road adhered to the speed limit of 30 km/h. The mean speed was 52 km/h and 25% of cars exceeded the speed limit assumed in the EIA by the factor of two.
- (5) Based on the measured traffic volume, car speeds and wildlife road mortalities we show that actual values of the three main anthropogenic factors determining the impact of the road upgrade on Natura 2000 site are much higher than those forecasted in the EIA report. This

constitutes an ultimate quality check for the EIA report used to issue the administrative decisions to upgrade the Narewowska road. The EIA report for the project in question consistently underestimated the magnitude of changes to car traffic, car speed and wildlife mortality for the upgraded road.

- (6) Using grossly underestimated values of main drivers of the anthropogenic impact of the upgraded road on the wildlife, the EIA could not properly estimate the true consequences of the upgrade project for the integrity of Natura 2000 site.
- (7) We suggest relevant authorities to implement mitigation measures aiming to effectively reduce speed of cars on the upgraded road as well as measures aiming to reduce the traffic volume.

5. Methods

5.1. Traffic measurements

We used a single camera-trap positioned close to Narewowska road to measure traffic volume on the road. The camera trap was operating 24 hrs per day for 489 days between 18 February 2019 and 06 October 2020. Within this time window, the camera trap was not operating for several series of days, due to technical problems. The camera shutter was released by the movement registered in the camera frame. In total, we analyzed 46,777 photographs.

The type of vehicle was assessed from photographs using the predefined list, which besides various cars, bicycles and motorbikes included also pedestrians and animals.

We modelled variation in the number of cars recorded per day using generalised linear models (GLM) with poisson error distribution which is routinely used for count data. We used road status (before or after the upgrade), month and day of the week as predictors, allowing for the interactions between status and month as well as status and day of the week:

$$\text{Daily number of cars} \sim \text{status} + \text{month} + \text{day} + \text{status:day} + \text{status:month}$$

Using this model we were able to estimate the effect of road upgrade on traffic volume while taking into account seasonal and weekly variation.

Models were fitted in R environment for statistical computations. Effect sizes were calculated using packages “effects” and “emmeans”.

For 17,463 photographs (37% of all records from the camera-trap), we were unable to find any object within the frame, but in most of these cases, it was possible to see the dust from the road surface freshly lifted in the air, suggestive of car that actually passed by but was moving too fast to be captured by the camera. This interpretation was supported by the highly non-random distribution of those events in time. Recorded times of taking these “ghost” pictures followed very closely times of recording actual cars. Modelled estimates of “ghosts” numbers and photographed car numbers showed highly concordant temporal patterns. This applies to the time of the day (Fig. M1, left panel), day of the week (Fig. M1, right panel), and month of the year (Fig. M2, left panel). Also, the frequency of “ghost” records increased sharply after the completed upgrade, mirroring closely the pattern found for the photographed cars (Fig.M2, right panel). Therefore, we are confident, that our “ghost” images represented fast-moving cars. Consequently, we treated the “ghost” images as cars in our analyses.

Fig. M1. Comparison of temporal patterns of records for photographed cars (red) and “ghost” images (green) shown for daily scale (left panel) and weekly scale (right panel). For the right panel shown are estimated means from the GLM model for cars per day as a function of status, month, and day of the week.

Fig. M2. Comparison of temporal patterns of records for photographed cars (red) and “ghost” images (green) shown for seasonal scale (left panel) and before/after upgrade status (right panel). Shown are estimated means from the GLM model for cars per day as a function of status, month, and day of the week.

5.2. Road mortality of wildlife

We performed 191 roadkill surveys of the road between 22 January 2019 and 01 June 2020, covering in total 2282 km*day of Narewowska road. During each visit, the observer walked or biked along the road, noted all recorded roadkills, and removed them from the road to avoid double counting. In total 509 vertebrates and 3239 invertebrates were recorded. In this study, we analysed vertebrates only.

The observed number of roadkills (i.e. 509) is underestimated due to three reasons: (1) some of the roadkills may be missing from the road surface, e.g. birds hit by the car or birds attached to the car. These roadkills are therefore not taken into account. (2) Road visits were performed every 2-5 days (every 2.6 days on average) so some roadkills can be removed by the scavengers before recorded by the observer. (3) Only part of the road was surveyed each time (on average 76.3% of the whole road section in question) so part of the roadkills was not included.

We, therefore, corrected the observed number of roadkills (509) to obtain true roadkills estimates. For this purpose, we left 21 vertebrate roadkills on the road (i.e. these kills were not removed) and estimated their “time to disappearance” on the road to learn how fast road carcasses are removed by scavengers. We recorded that, on average, roadkill disappears after 177 hours (range: 10-682 hours). Next, with the help of resampling of the 21 roadkills (100 replications), we simulated variation of the “time to disappearance” and modelled this data with the help of generalised linear model with binomial error structure, explaining the proportion of roadkills left on the road (in theory ranging from 0 to 1) as a function of time elapsed since the collision. As an effect, the model helped us to estimate the correction factor separately for each control, depending on the time that elapsed since the preceding control. The correction factor was then used to calculate the total estimated number of vertebrate roadkills. Finally, we recalculated the estimated roadkill number to the total length of the road, i.e. 15.6 km.

We used generalised linear models to relate the number of roadkills to the intensity of car traffic on the road (as measured by the camera traps).

5.3. Car speed

We have measured speed of cars driving Narewowska road on 05-06 June 2021 using two persons measuring the exact time when individual cars (identified by their licence plates) passed each of the two measurement points located 10.5 km away along the road. The survey was conducted between 10:00 and 16:00 and 11:00 and 13:00. To obtain speed estimates we divided distance of 10.5 km by the time used to drive between the two measurement points. As such, the speed estimates refer only to the period after the road upgrade.

5.4. Author contributions

All the field work and majority of data analyses were conducted by our co-workers who wished to remain anonymous. We (PC and NS) have designed the work, repeated and extended the data analyses and prepared the text of the report.